

Krypton, applied as refrigerant for cooling of silicon detector trackers

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ABSTRACT

The thermal management of highly irradiated silicon detectors may soon require cooling temperatures beyond the limits of -45°C for the currently applied technologies with CO_2 . The working fluid shall be able to approach ultra-low temperatures for large heat loads using small piping and withstand a significant amount of radiation. Among the short-listed candidates, the noble gas krypton appears as an interesting alternative for the future cooling infrastructure of particle trackers at CERN.

In this work, the use of Krypton is investigated. Its favorable thermodynamic properties are analyzed with respect to the very harsh operational requirements present inside high energy particle detectors. A preliminary design of a low-temperature refrigeration cycle is proposed, and different transient scenarios commonly encountered during real-life detector operation are evaluated.

Keywords: Refrigeration, Krypton, Carbon Dioxide, Supercritical.

1. INTRODUCTION

CO_2 (R744) has been adopted as the de-facto refrigerant used for particle detectors since its first application in the LHCb Velo detector in 2008 because of its ability of using small channels thanks to the high working pressure, which leads to low temperature gradients. The radiation hardness of CO_2 plays also an important role while low toxicity, low flammability, and the possibility to distribute the refrigerant using an oil-free mechanically pumped loop commonly referred as 2PACL (Verlaat, Lysebetten et al. 2008) are additional advantageous features. High-pressure refrigerants are particularly advantageous as smaller pipes can be used to reduce the amount of passive material in the tracking region, while an oil free solution is mandatory to avoid the oil degradation and decomposition into a corrosive compounds due to high level of irradiation (Petagna, Verlaat et al. 2018).

The targeted operational temperatures for HEP (High Energy Physics) detectors have been lowered over the years stretching the CO_2 to its limit, represented by the triple point temperature of -56°C . Future detectors will require a new high pressure refrigerant candidate that can go colder while keeping the low interaction with the tracking process of the particles and the level of safety typical of CO_2 . Among the refrigerants considered in this work, Krypton (R784) stands out as a promising candidate to be used in future detectors to operate in the ultra-low temperature range between -60°C and -100°C . Both sub-and supercritical use is considered.

This paper starts by describing the main requirements of silicon detectors followed by a list of potential refrigerant candidates. An extensive analysis is carried out, pointing at Krypton as the most favourable solution. Finally, a complete new supercritical refrigeration cycle is proposed with the capability to work both in the sub-and supercritical via a special transcritical cooldown method according to the detector temperature requirements.

2. CHALLENGES FOR REFRIGERANTS AS COOLANTS OF HEP DETECTORS

The cooling requirements of HEP detector experiments differ from conventional refrigeration systems. For instance, detectors require that all the instrumentation of the cooling system is placed far from the irradiated area for maintenance during operation. The return of the refrigerant is in two-phase to benefit at the same time from the high heat transfer coefficient in the low-quality steam region and from operating condition far from the risk of dryout. Moreover, the temperature level at the evaporators shall be controlled remotely. Finally, as these experiments are installed underground, the system footprint shall be reduced and the refrigerant safe (low flammability and low toxicity).

Furthermore, the CERN policy towards only environmental-friendly refrigerants (CERN 2017/2018) shall be considered in selecting the potential candidates.

2.1. Silicon detector

The more a silicon detector is irradiated by the crossing of particles, the colder it must be to keep the heat dissipated by the sensor leakage current at its minimum. The total radiation damage and the silicon detector technology are hence the main factors determining the temperature level of the cooling system.

For the High Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) phase of ATLAS and CMS, the silicon detectors placed close to the beam pipe will need to withstand ten times more radiation than what the current detectors will see at their end-of-life. To avoid the thermal runaway on the sensors, the cooling systems are required to provide cooling at -40°C (Barroca 2019) which will be guaranteed by a modular CO_2 transcritical booster system (Barroca, Hafner et al. 2021) and a scaled up version of the 2PACL CO_2 system currently used to cool the Inner B-Layer detector (Verlaat, Ostrega et al. 2017). For the next generation of detectors, assuming the radiation levels will continue to increase, the required temperatures are expected to get below the -56°C limit of CO_2 (ECFA 2020). The detectors must stay cold at all times, even when the power is off.

The choice of the refrigerant for the future detectors shall hence reduce the temperature level while not compromising the very favourable properties of CO_2 cooling system like low lack of flammability, low toxicity, radiation hardness and reduced overall radiation length thanks to the use of small pipes.

2.2. Cooling strategy

As the power dissipation is sensitive to the temperature, having a homogeneous temperature across all detectors is very appreciated so every silicon detector operates at the same conditions. To comply with this requirement, the detector evaporators shall be flooded to guarantee two-phase mixture inside evaporators and wetted walls (vapour quality at the outlet under 40%-50%) while in evaporative cooling mode.

Differently from conventional cooling systems, the temperature level at the evaporators shall be finely controlled from room temperature down to the low temperature setpoint, to avoid thermal shock at the silicon detectors as they are arguably the most sensitive and critical element in a HEP particle detector.

2.3. Natural working fluid candidates

The list of natural refrigerants in the temperature domain below the triple point of R744, -56°C , is very limited. Nitrous oxide (R744A) has similar critical point as R744 but much lower freezing point which makes it a suitable fluid to be used as a R744 freezing point depressant (Nicola, Giuliani et al. 2005, Kruse and Rüssmann 2006, Nicola, Giuliani et al. 2007). Nitrous oxide is an oxidizing agent which can decompose explosively under certain operating conditions, and its use in pure form is not recommended. To increase the protection against explosion risks the CO_2 concentration can be raised but a lower possible evaporating temperature can be reached as countereffect (Kauffeld, Maurath et al. 2020). However, $\text{N}_2\text{O}-\text{CO}_2$ mixtures result a low-pressure working fluid in the two-phase region of interest leading to low efficiency and extremely high pressure-temperature gradients when small diameter pipes are adopted. All in all, the additional safety measures required to minimize risk of explosion and flammability and the low operating pressures, would hold back its use especially being an underground application and in view of future further extension of the

low operational temperature range. This mixture remains however a solution for cooling low heat flux applications at temperatures below -56°C (Verlaet 2021). Hydrocarbons (HCs) like ethane and ethylene are known for their good thermodynamic properties, but their use in underground facilities is prohibited due to their flammability.

The other options include the noble gases Krypton and Xenon which are monoatomic, colourless, odourless and non-flammable with very low melting and boiling points. The molecular structure of those elements make them the hardest element in nature and suitable for applications in a highly irradiated environment (Furtado, De Proft et al. 2015).

These fluids can be however very expensive as they are not widely available in the market. Their applications regard mostly lighting and ion engines (spacecraft applications). Krypton has been however already considered to be used in adsorption chillers for aerospace applications (Jones and Schember 1989).

2.4. Thermodynamic properties

Relevant thermophysical properties of the candidates are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Comparison of thermodynamic properties among the different coolants.

The lower latent heat of vaporization, the faster the vapor quality increases in the evaporator assuming the same flow rate. To avoid the risk of dry-out at extremely high reduced pressure, the system must operate with higher mass flow rate. The liquid viscosity is a measure of resistance of a fluid to flow and a lower liquid viscosity with a low surface tension facilitates the boiling process. A large density ratio between liquid and vapor density would lead to large pressure drops along the cooling pipes, with a consequent temperature gradient on the detector side. It is worth to mention that the cooling domain for the future HEP detectors will probably range from -50°C down to -80°C , meaning that with Krypton, there would be a distinction between a heating process in supercritical region (gas heating) and a usual evaporation process in subcritical state. All the other candidates have a relatively high critical temperature.

The supercritical region is a mono-phase region with favourable properties for heat and mass transfer, mainly thanks to large heat capacity and very low viscosity. In this region all the properties have a strong change at the vicinity of the pseudocritical point, i.e. the temperature for a given pressure at which the specific heat reaches its maximum. Figure 2 shows various physical properties of Krypton versus temperature at different pressure levels in the supercritical region.

Figure 2: Physical properties of supercritical Krypton at different pressures versus temperatures.

The peak of specific heat becomes narrower and sharper as the operative pressure approaches the critical one. The magnitude of this peak, both for specific heat and liquid thermal conductivity, decreases very quickly with an increase in pressure. The density and dynamic viscosity undergo a significant drop near the critical point. All in all, the rapid change of the physical and transport properties of Krypton will strongly influence heat transfer and pressure drops. Closer to the critical point the heat transfer process is governed by local conditions due to the strong physical property effects caused by the temperature gradients at a given pressure. As evaluated in literature for supercritical CO₂, a distinction between the gas cooling and heating must be done (Pitla, Robinson et al. 1998, Cheng, Ribatski et al. 2008). The heat transfer performance is significantly affected by the buoyancy forces in some conditions. A large temperature difference is an essential condition where those forces impact the heat transfer. All in all, working above the critical point could ensure better heat transfer performance but it is strongly dependent on the wall temperature and the convective mechanism of “pseudo boiling” associated with the density gradient which can lead to an enhancement or deterioration of the heat transfer (Wang, Ma et al. 2021). A special design of the cooling lines with the aim of having as much as possible a homogenous cooling over all the detectors is required.

2.5. Heat transfer performance

The volumetric heat transfer coefficient, which accounts for temperature drops due to heat transfer and pressure losses as a part of the thermal chain is the preferable way to find the best cooling choices for HEP (Verlaet and Petagna 2019). The volumetric heat transfer coefficient is defined via the equation (1):

$$\text{Volumetric heat transfer} = \frac{Q}{V_{\text{tube}} * \Delta T(\Delta P + HTC)} \quad (1)$$

Where the temperature difference between the lowest fluid temperature and warmest temperature in the tube ($\Delta T(\Delta P + HTC)$) accounts both for the HTC and frictional losses. The thermal gradients along the thermal chain from the heat source (sensors) to the heat sink (cooling pipe) must be minimized according to the thermal management design constraints (Petagna, Verlaet et al. 2018). Alongside this, the radiation length (mass) (Gupta 2010) which indicates the perturbation to the tracking process should be minimized as well. A balance between thermal gradients and radiation length (mass) must therefore be considered.

Here, the cooling tube performance is maximized. In this respect, the optimization of the cooling pipe dimensions is conducted based on different criteria such as lowest mass or smallest pipe. The volumetric heat transfer copes the increase of heat transfer coefficient with an increase of the friction losses by adopting smaller diameters, enabling to find out the optimal diameter (Figure 3). A heat transfer correlation from Kandlikar (Kandlikar 1990) and the pressure drop correlation of Friedel (Friedel 1979) have been used for the calculations. A standard detector with its relative length, heat load and vapor quality range has been considered for the calculation according to (ECFA 2020).

Figure 3: Cooling tube performance and optimal diameter for Krypton (L = 2 [m], Q = 200 W, T = -80 °C, vapor quality range = 0 – 0.35).

The optimal diameter has been identified around 1.8 mm for the case specified. It can be seen how at smaller pipe diameters the temperature drops among wall-refrigerant decreases due to the enhancement of the heat transfer thanks to higher flow speed; on the contrary, the pressure losses increase due to the higher mass fluxes and friction losses. The performance of the different fluids investigated is illustrated in (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Volumetric heat transfer coefficient of different refrigerants (L = 2[m], Q = 200 [W], T = -80 [°C], vapor quality range = 0 – 0.35).

Figure 4 shows the better heat transfer performance of high-pressure fluids. Krypton overcomes all the other candidates with a higher volumetric heat transfer. Being Krypton a high-working pressure fluid, by having a smaller pipe diameter the pressure losses and corresponding temperature drop in the subcritical domain are relatively low, leading to a smaller thermal resistance for convection (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Cooling tube performance in terms of thermal resistance (L = 2 [m], Q = 200 W, T = -80 °C, vapor quality range = 0 – 0.35).

The HCs, N₂O and Xenon present lower reduced pressures and consequently the temperature drops are larger, strongly penalizing the use of those fluids at the temperature level investigated. At lower pressures, the pressure gradient should be contained to achieve low temperature gradients. If any refrigerant except Krypton is used, it must be accepted a much lower capability of removing heat for a given control volume while strongly impacting the mass optimization target due to the larger pipe diameters. All in all, the

possibility of accepting higher pressure losses for Krypton allows higher velocities and thus higher heat transfer coefficients. This ends up by showing as Krypton is the most promising candidate investigated from the heat transfer performance point of view. It is worth to mention that the minimization of the cooling pipe diameter is a simplified method to find the best cooling choices for HEP because the space saved in terms of pipe volume is replaced by other materials which normally present larger resistances. In this sense, a deeper study on the total mass specific heat transfer should be conducted with the aim of getting the full picture for a given refrigerant, incorporating the radiation length as well.

For temperature above the critical point of Krypton, further investigation must be conducted. The behavior of a supercritical fluid with a continuous and rapid change of thermophysical properties, as well as the possible mechanism triggered by temperature gradients both in the radial and transverse direction, is still unknown. In any way, the expected heat transfer coefficient is relatively high and in the range of 4-5000 W/m²K according to different studies (Liao and Zhao 2002, Dang and Hihara 2004, Cheng, Ribatski et al. 2008, Huang, Wu et al. 2016, Guo, Liu et al. 2020).

3. HYBRID CYCLE WITH KRYPTON

The current cooling unit operating with CO₂ is based on a subcooled pumped loop (Bhanot, Petagna et al. 2020) where the heat is rejected via a CO₂ primary chiller. The proposed cooling unit with Krypton aims to use oil-free machines as turbocompressors replacing the two-phase pumped loop with a hybrid refrigeration cycle but still requiring a primary CO₂ chiller to reject heat. Using oil-lubricated compressors has been discarded as it is very hard to avoid the injection of oil in the recirculating refrigerant regardless the high efficiency of the oil separators, which is an unacceptable risk for this specific application. Under strong irradiation the oil droplets could polymerize potentially clogging the pipes and produce corrosive compounds (Petagna, Verlaat et al. 2018).

One technical challenge introduced by the use of turbocompressors is the strong influence of the pressure ratio in the volumetric flow that may impose their operation with a fixed pressure ratio. Furthermore, heavy refrigerants in terms of molecular weight are favoured as they reduce the number of stages required for a given temperature lift. The refrigeration unit shall be able to cool down the detector gently from room temperature at the start-up. A typical 1 K/min is common practise in particle detectors. The slow cool down is needed to not damage the sensitive light weight support structures. The vapor phase of Krypton at ambient conditions requires a transcritical cooldown cycle able to cool down slowly the detector by controlling the charge and high-pressure level. Hybrid cycle hereby presented is able to work both in sub-and supercritical state without interruptions of the unit. The transition between different operating modes is achieved by activating different components of the system according to the temperature and pressure level, solving the issue of a thermal shock when starting from room temperature towards extremely low temperatures. Figure 6 illustrates the refrigeration unit proposed.

The proposed configuration involves a turbo-compression stage (A-B), a cold gas-bypass valve (C-A), a gas cooler section (B-D), a high-pressure control section (F-G), an internal subcooler (D-F), a concentric line among inlet-outlet of the detector (G-H), a liquid receiver and an external tank filled with supercritical fluid. The cycle starts by injecting supercritical Krypton stored in the pressurized tank at room temperature into the unit (charging). The turbocompressors must work with a pressure ratio almost constant to avoid any fluid dynamics problem overpassing the surge envelope. Stable control of the volumetric flow rate is crucial to preserve a good efficiency and a constant rotational speed. The change in vapor density over the transcritical envelope leads to different volumetric flow rates, necessarily requiring a proper sizing of the compressor pack. The compressors always control the detector operational pressure. The CGBV controls the cooling capacity: in the transcritical region the mass flow through the detector is regulated according to the maximum temperature gradient allowed (usually $\approx 3/5$ K) while during flow boiling of Krypton through the detector channels the vapor quality change must be prioritized. The CO₂ gas cooler section consists in two parts: the first gas cooler cools down the Krypton to a temperature such to not induce a huge mixing at the suction line of the turbocompressors. The second gas cooler aims to keep under control the detector inlet

temperature for supercritical conditions. The temperature regulation due the thermal inertia is usually difficult to handle, and it is time consuming. In this respect, during supercritical condition the possibility to further charge the unit acts as a buffer against a possible collapse of the pressure and consequent thermal shock of the detector, while gaining one more degree of freedom towards a more robust control of the detector operation. The expansion valve regulates the upstream pressure to maintain an almost constant pressure ratio, according to the suction pressure. The concentric line acts as countereffect against fast overcooling of the detector in supercritical state while provides saturated liquid at the entrance of the detector, resulting in an easier distribution through the multi-branched channels. It is imperative to avoid boiling of refrigerant before the entrance of the channels, otherwise the flow separation would feed some channels with only vapor dramatically increasing the risk of dry-out (Verlaat 2013).

Figure 6: Simplified PID of the refrigeration unit operating with Krypton.

3.1. Start-up challenges

At the ambient temperature normally registered in the underground cavern ($\approx 20^{\circ}\text{C}$), the system would be filled by Krypton in gas phase. When the detector starts to be cooled down, a gas heating of Krypton occurs otherwise subcritical evaporation would result in a thermal shock. However, the starting point for the compression unit can be controlled according to the charge: the supercritical tank delivers refrigerant into the unit by further increasing the pressure and based on the charging rate the starting pressure levels (suction and discharge) can be estimated. When the required pressure in the unit is reached, the injection stops, and the compressors start. As indicated with the red line in Figure 6, after compression, the refrigerant is cooled down by a first CO_2 gas cooler stage. Downstream, the controlled gas by-pass valve (CGBV) would ensure a controlled removal of heat. The cooling load (only thermal dissipation to the environment) can continuously

be controlled by throttling the refrigerant back to the suction of the compressors. The remaining amount of Krypton is then cooled down through the 2nd CO₂ gas cooler according to the temperature level. As more heat is rejected to the CO₂ side, the suction pressure will start decrease and thus the charging process must account for it in order not to cross the two-phase region in the low-pressure side. After that, the refrigerant is throttled before entering in a concentric line where the warmer return line heats up the inlet flow, further reducing the heat load and functioning as safety to avoid a fast overcooling of the detector. Then the refrigerant flows through a tank and an internal subcooler before being sucked by the turbocompressors and the cycle restarts. The first cool-down stage deals with several challenges: ensuring a stable and controlling the cooling rate of the detector, a stable low and high pressures through the compression stage and high-pressure valve respectively. Figure 7 illustrates the dynamic process in the p-h diagram with the aim of describing the working principle and not the entity of heating/cooling.

Figure 7: Start-up mode with the pressurization process with the supercritical tank followed by gentle detector cooling (A-B: compression, B-C: 1st stage GC with R744, C-A: CGBV, D-E: expansion, E-F: heating inlet concentric line, F-G: cooling of detector, G-A: cooling return concentric line).

3.2. Supercritical operation

When the operating envelope hits the cooling limit of CO₂, an internal subcooling using Krypton is needed to reduce the temperature level and the reason is two-fold: on one hand, if R744 was not used it would be required another natural working fluid with a lower freezing point. On the other hand, whenever subcritical conditions occur, the limit to the maximum acceptable vapor quality imposed to avoid risks of dry-out in the detector would result in a two-phase flow in the return line that couldn't be handled by the compression stage. Therefore, a further cooling beyond the freezing point of CO₂ and vaporization of the two-phase mixture can be achieved through an internal subcooling (Figure 8). At this point, when the detector inlet temperature is around -60°C, the heat load of several hundred of kW can be removed if needed while operating fully in supercritical region.

It is worth mentioning that during the gas heating process, a temperature gradient along the detector occurs. If the detector is not in operation and the heat load is low (heat dissipated to the environment increases by going colder), the temperature gradient is relatively small according to the mass of refrigerant. If the aim is an isothermal cooling to avoid as low as possible change in the coefficient of thermal expansion and

misalignment of sensor temperatures, the following approach could be followed: after the first stages, some pressure drops could be introduced voluntarily to achieve an isothermal cooling along the evaporator length. When the operating conditions move much closer to the critical point, the steep isothermal lines become less inclined drastically requiring less pressure drops introduced but considering a higher flow rate.

Figure 8: Supercritical operation with internal subcooler (D-E & I-A internal subcooling – superheating).

3.3. Transcritical-subcritical operation

The hybrid cycle presented above can cover both sub- and supercritical operating conditions. The supercritical mode is active until the detector operational temperature is above the critical point of Krypton. The expected radiation levels in the ATLAS ITk will increase in the future further requiring cooling at lower temperature and thus a new operational mode of the cycle. In this scenario, evaporative cooling is required during the lifetime of the detectors. This mainly required the transition from a fully supercritical cycle towards a transcritical – subcritical cycle as described in Figure 9, where the detector operational pressure can be accurately controlled by the turbocompressors as long as the pressure drop of return line is sufficiently low:

In this transition, the receiver aims to first separate the two phases and then to control the amount of liquid to be mixed at the entrance of the subcooler on the low-pressure side. The temperature at the gas cooler outlet must be controlled in a way to start expanding on the left side of the dome to keep lines liquified avoiding uneven flow distribution in the manifolds. By doing so, the concentric line enables the subcooling of the inlet flow by further vaporizing the outlet two-phase flow of the detector. When the heat removed is low and the high-pressure level is relatively high, the heat rejection through the 2nd stage of gas cooling must be controlled accordingly to the superheat setpoint at the suction of the compressors. At lower heat rejection pressure, the load in the CO₂ gas coolers is dramatically reduced and the heat rejection through the internal subcooler is predominant.

Figure 9: Transcritical operation of the hybrid cycle with the aim of reaching cold temperatures in the range $-70/-80$ °C (1-2 & 3-4 is the heat exchanged inside the internal subcooler).

If the target operational temperature reaches -80 °C, when the detector is active the heat load removed causes an increase of the vapor quality. Such increment of the outlet vapor quality may lead to an unstable control of the high-pressure which may make difficult the control of the operational conditions inside the detector (Figure 10). In this case, the heat available on the low-pressure side would be insufficient to maintain the desired level of subcooling and the only option to overcome it would be to increase the flow rate through the detector. This possible solution to reach temperatures below -80 °C must be carefully evaluated by considering pressure losses, the design of the manifolds and potential disturbance of the particle tracking process.

Figure 10: Transcritical operation of the hybrid cycle at -80 °C.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, different refrigerant candidates to cool the future highly irradiated detectors have been explored. The ultra-low temperature domain further reduces the list of possible cooling media and requires a rethink of the cooling process. Different candidates have been compared in terms thermophysical properties and volumetric heat transfer coefficient. The use of HCs has been discarded for underground applications due to their high flammability while the noble gas Xenon presents poor heat transfer performance. Nitrous oxide (N₂O) presents a very low reduced pressure in the temperature range of interest and hence, it cannot compete with a high-pressure fluid as Krypton. Consequently, all mixtures involving N₂O as additive are suitable for low heat flux cooling in the temperature domain below CO₂. Krypton stands out as the most promising refrigerant to be used with small piping and at very low temperatures unachievable with CO₂.

A novel hybrid cooling cycle to cool down future silicon detectors is proposed. The process comprises both supercritical and subcritical operation and different scenarios have been explored. The control strategy to meet required cooling down time and avoid a thermal shock has been proposed as possible solutions to overcome the challenges during the start-up mode and at the lowest temperatures required during the detector life-time in subcritical mode.

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NOMENCLATURE

<i>R784</i>	Krypton	<i>IHX</i>	Internal heat exchanger
<i>R744</i>	Carbon dioxide	<i>Q</i>	Heat load [W]
<i>R744A</i>	Nitrous oxide	ΔT	Temperature gradient [K]
<i>HCS</i>	Hydrocarbons	ΔP	Pressure gradient [bar]
<i>HEP</i>	High Energy Physics	<i>HTC</i>	Heat transfer coefficient [$W/m^2 \cdot K$]
<i>LHC</i>	Large Hadron Collider		

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